

Introducing trees in beef cattle grazing areas

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One of the difficulties encountered when livestock is grazing is to provide the appropriate amount and nutritional value of the grass storey of pastures which can be reduced as a result of drought periods. As the climate changes, the risk of irregularities and unpredictability is increases.

Open pastures during colder or hot periods increase animal stress, decline animal health and decrease feeding efficiency. Non tree-protected pastures strengthen the risk of soil losses as well. Plantation of trees or using existing woodlots offer solution to these problems. Wooded pastures provide foodstuff such as acorn, wild fruits, herbs or foliage by which food supply to livestock can be diversified and even ensured.

These sources also contain antiviral, fungicide, bactericide and immune-supportive agents that can play an important role in maintaining or improving animal health. In addition, trees create nesting places for birds that according to farmers decrease nuisance and harmfulness of flies for livestock promoting health and good quality livestock products.

They rub themselves against trees or enjoy the shade on warmer days or shelter during windy cold days. Caretaking, manifested among others in the diversification of grazing resource practices will result in good quality beef. Moreover, such areas provide wood (renewable fuel) as well, by which the price of thinning can be covered.

Figure 1. Having rest in forage patches. Ref: Mozsi Ranch, Sellye, Hungary

Figure 2. Grazing in woodland Ref: OIKOS Farm, Krzywa, Poland

Further Information:

http://www.eurafagroforestry.eu/files/pub/20190804_factsheet_29_en_web.pdf

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